

Hatchling Gila monster (*Heloderma suspectum*) in Rotterdam Zoo

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The habitat of *Heloderma suspectum* in the Sonora desert.

Photo: www.reflectiveimages.com

INTRODUCTION

In the family Helodermatidae there are only two venomous lizards: *Heloderma suspectum* and *Heloderma horridum*. The venom glands of *Heloderma* are in the lower jaw, unlike those of the poisonous snakes. The teeth are grooved but not hollow. The venom empties into the mouth through several ducts that open between the teeth and the lips. *Heloderma* bites and retains a firm grasp while it chews, thus enhancing the entry of the venom into the wound. Their bite is painful, but seldom fatal to humans (see also: SHANNON, 1953). The species can reach a size of 30-35 cm snout-vent length. A maximum of 50 cm total length has been recorded.

The natural habitats are deserts and arid areas. The family Helodermatidae is distributed from the southwestern USA to Mexico and Guatemala. *Heloderma suspectum* is found in the USA (southeastern California, southern Nevada, southwestern Utah, Arizona), and Mexico (Sonora). The animals usually live a solitary existence, are active during the daytime, and retreat into underground burrows to rest. They have large home ranges of several hectares. Their food is found both above and underground as they are good climbers and diggers (EMBL database).

BREEDING GROUP

The Rotterdam Zoo (Diergaarde Blijdorp) has kept Gila monsters, *Heloderma suspectum*, for over two decades. During this period, the animals seemed healthy but breeding attempts were unsuccessful. In 2000, four animals were transferred to a new enclosure in the Sonoran desert habitat of the new *Oceanium* building, the part called 'Sea of Cortez'. It was believed that the improved temperature regime there – in winter the temperature is allowed to drop to as low as 12°C – would be the main key to a successful breeding. Also the fact that there were three males to one female was regarded as beneficial to the mating process, because it would enable the males to perform their ritualised combat.

The adult group in Blijdorp consists of two males that were donated by the Dallas Zoo (USA) in 1999, and a male and a female that came from two different private breeders.

The enclosure in the Sonoran desert habitat of the new *Oceanium* building in which the *Heloderma suspectum* live. At the time this picture was taken (Dec. 2002) the adults hibernate in holes (one such opening is visible).

Photo: G. Visser

EUROPE - ROTTERDAM

No Gila monsters have hatched in European Zoos since the early nineties. In Glasgow four young hatched in 1989 and ten in 1991, and in London Zoo one young was obtained in 1989 (source: ISIS).

In Rotterdam Zoo (Diergaarde Blijdorp) our first ever Gila monster *Heloderma suspectum* hatched on 18 November 2002. The egg pipped on the 16th and the hatchling emerged from the egg during the night of the 17th. A double slit was visible in the leathery shell of the egg on the 16th and the head emerged on the following day. We found the youngster had totally emerged by the morning of the 18th. The hatchling measured 16.5 cm and weighed 49.5 grams. It was the sole hatchling from a clutch of five eggs that were laid on July 5th. The eggs were incubated at 28°C at a relatively low humidity of 65% and hatched after 137 days. The remainder of the eggs proved to be infertile, or possibly died off at a very early stage. These data compare well to the report of EIDENMÜLLER & WICKER (1992), who give an incubation period of 128 days, but they incubated at a higher temperature (four weeks at 27.5°C, the remainder of the period at 29°C).

The hatchling seems to be doing well and has started feeding readily on dead pink mice. The rather large hatchling is fed twice weekly and gets 2-3 pinkies per meal. Of course a mineral/vitamin supplement is added to the food.

In the wild Gila Monsters feed on a wide variety of animal food – mainly nestling rodents, but also lizards, and occasionally on bird and reptile eggs.

The EMBL database reports that courtship and mating occur from late April to early June, and 2-12 eggs are laid in mid-July to mid-August. Eggs are 67 to 75 mm long and 33 to 39 mm wide. They are buried to depths of about 125 mm in an open place that is exposed to

the sun, but usually near a stream or dry wash. The eggs overwinter, hatching after about 10 months in May. In captivity or under optimal conditions the incubation time is only about 30 days. According to our information these latter data are inaccurate, as incubation durations are between 120-140 days, and only occasionally does a clutch overwinter. In nature hatchlings most probably still have the opportunity to feed before they start hibernating. In October and November temperatures in Arizona reach 30-25°C respectively, which is certainly high enough for the lizards to be active.

The freshly hatched *Heloderma suspectum*.

Photo: G. Visser

BREEDING IN ZOOS

Propagation in zoos primarily serves to maintain a zoo population, and by so doing eliminates the need to obtain animals from the wild. It also has the additional purpose of being an 'assurance' population, a reservoir of animals if anything disastrous happens in the natural habitat. For both motives, genetic management is applied to assure as varied a gene pool as possible. There is also a breeding program for the other species, *Heloderma horridum*, run by the EEP (see note below). This species has been bred in the Zürich Zoo (HONEGGER, 1998).

Combined with the recent successful hatching in the Zoo of Jihlava, Czech republic (where four young hatched between 14-19 November 2002), these are the first births for *Heloderma suspectum* within the EEP-programme in eleven years.

EEP stands for European Endangered species Programme. The actual acronym (missing the S) dates back from the times that the Germans thought that their language would become the medium of communication within the European zoo society: Europäisches Erhaltungszucht Programm. The EEP is co-ordinated by Usti nad Labem, Czech Republic (Dr. Jaroslav Zima), see ZIMA (2002).

SUMMARY

The first hatchling of *Heloderma suspectum* in twenty years is reported in the Rotterdam Zoo. The improved temperature regime in their new housing, with high summer and low winter readings, is thought to have been instrumental to this success. As well, the ratio of three males to one female, which allows for ritualised combats, is probably also beneficial.

LITERATURE

- EIDENMÜLLER, B. & R. WICKER, 1992. Über eine Nachzucht von *Heloderma suspectum* (Cope, 1869). Salamandra 28: 106-111.
- EMBL DATABASE. <http://www.embl-heidelberg.de/~uetz/LivingReptiles.html>
- HONEGGER, R.E., 1998. Beitrag zu Haltung und Zucht der Skorpionkrustenechse, *Heloderma horridum*, im Zoo Zürich. Zool. Garten N. F. 68(5): 287-299.
- ISIS* <http://156.99.114.200/>
<https://www.isis.org/abstracts/abs.asp>
- SHANNON, F.A., 1953. Case reports of two Gila monster bites. Herpetologica 9: 25-27.
- ZIMA, J., 2002. The 2001 Gila monster (*Heloderma suspectum*) and beaded lizard (*Heloderma horridum*). E.E.P. studbook, Usti nad Labem.
- Internet links were last checked on December 2, 2002.

* ISIS: International Species Information System – a co-ordinating zoo system, based in the USA that keeps records of the hundreds of affiliated zoos using ARKS (Animal Record Keeping Systems).